

Strategic Deciphering of Salmonella SiiE Adhesin Specificity for Advanced Anti-Adhesion Therapy

Alicia Candeias^{1,2}, Benedita Pinheiro^{1,2}, Filipa Trovão^{1,2}, Antonio Di Maio³,
Wengang Chai³, Ten Feizi³, Yan Liu³, Aldino Viegas^{1,2}, Angelina Sá Palma^{1,2},
Filipa Marcelo^{1,2}, Helena Coelho^{1,2*}

¹Associate Laboratory i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of
Science and Technology, NOVA University of Lisbon, Caparica 2829-516, Portugal

²UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Depart. of Chemistry, NOVA School of
Science and Technology, NOVA University of Lisbon, Caparica 2829-516, Portugal

³Glycosciences Laboratory, Department of Metabolism, Digestion and Reproduction,
Imperial College London, W12 0NN, London, United Kingdom.

h.coelho@fct.unl.pt

Salmonellosis is a major foodborne health concern, with 1.35 million cases reported annually in the U.S., resulting in 26,500 hospitalizations and 420 deaths¹. The rise of antibiotic-resistant strains and the economic burden of disease management highlight the urgent need for new therapeutic strategies targeting *Salmonella*.

Salmonella adheres to host cells through specific interactions between bacterial adhesins and host cell receptors, often involving glycoproteins and glycans¹.

The non-fibrillar *Salmonella* SiiE giant adhesin targets Mucin-1 (MUC1) via sialic acid- containing O-glycans, playing a pivotal role in infection². Understanding SiiE's specificity and molecular interactions with mucin O-glycans is crucial for targeting the SiiE-MUC1 interaction, offering an alternative approach to combat bacterial resistance. Our methodology integrates glycan microarrays, mucin cell-based arrays, and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) for high-throughput screening and detailed insights into molecular structure and dynamics. This approach is essential for understanding SiiE's molecular specificity, facilitating the development of novel anti-adhesion molecules to combat *Salmonella* infections.

References

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2. Li, X. et al. *PLoS Pathog.* **2019**, 15, e1007566

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